

Study The Class of Univalent Functions In View of Ratios for Partial Sums and Derivatives.

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Abstract

This paper is concern with the new class $O_\lambda^\eta(\xi, \alpha, \beta, \partial, \lambda, l, u)$ of schlicht functions. We studied the real parts for different ratios of the functions in the class $O_\lambda^\eta(\xi, \alpha, \beta, \partial, \lambda, l, u)$. The sharp lower bounds for $\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{b(z)}{b_n(z)} \right\}$, $\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{b_n(z)}{b(z)} \right\}$, $\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{b'(z)}{b_n'(z)} \right\}$, $\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{b_n'(z)}{b'(z)} \right\}$ is obtained.

Keywords: Univalent function, differential operator

Introduction

$\mathcal{F}$ be the class of all schlicht functions of the form $b(z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \rho_k z^k$ (1.1) on open unit disc $D = \{z: |z| < 1\}$.

Functions of the form (1.1) are normalized with condition $b(0) = 0, b'(0) = 1$.

The partial sums for the function in (1.1) is denoted by $b_n(z)$

$$b_n(z) = z + \sum_{k=2}^n \rho_k z^k \quad (1.2)$$

[7] has introduced Ruschwey differential operator as given bellow,

Definition 1.1. $U^n: \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$ defined by

$$\begin{aligned} U^n(b(z)) &= \frac{z}{(1-z)^{n+1}} \cdot b(z) & n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\} \\ &= z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \binom{n+k-1}{n} \rho_k z^k & (z \in D) \end{aligned} \quad (1.3)$$

Where $(.)$ is hadmard product defined by [10].

We note that $U^0 b(z) = b(z), U^1 b(z) = zb(z)$.

[4, 7, 8, 9] has used this operator to study the geometric properties for the classes of normalized univalent functions. [14] has introduced Generalized Aloboudi differential operator . It is also known as Opoola differential operator. The expression for this operator is as follows:

Definition 1.2. [2] has introduced Opoola differential operator as follows:

$D^n: \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$ defined by

$$D^0(u, l, \square) b(z) = b(z) \quad (1.4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} D^1(u, l, \square) b(z) &= \square z b'(z) - z((1-u)\square f(z) + (1 + (1-u-1)\square)b(z)) \\ &= zD_{\square} b(z) \quad \square \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (1.5)$$

$$D^2(u, l, \square) b(z) = zD_{\square}(zD_{\square} b(z)) \quad (1.6)$$

$$D^n(u, l, \square) b(z) = zD_{\square}(D^{n-1}(u, l, \square) b(z)) \quad (1.7)$$

From (1.6) and (1.7) we have

$$D^n(u, l, \square) (b(z)) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} [1 + (k+l-u-1)\partial]^n \rho_k z^k \quad (z \in U) \quad (1.8)$$

Where $0 \leq u \leq l$.

[2][8][9] has used this operator to obtain coefficient, extreme points and other properties for different classes of normalized univalent functions.

[8] has introduced Rusal differential operator which is convex combination of Al-Oboudi and Ruschweyh derivative operator. Here we make the convex combination of Ruschweyh and Opoola differential operator.

Definition 1.3. Let $n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, \lambda \geq 0, O_\lambda^n: \mathcal{F} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$ defined by

$$O_\lambda^n(b(z)) = (1-\lambda) D^n(u, l, \square) (b(z)) + \lambda R^n b(z). \quad (1.9)$$

On simplifying we observed that,

$$O_\lambda^n(f(z)) = z + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} ([1 + (k+l-u-1)\partial]^n (1-\lambda) + \lambda \binom{n+k-1}{n}) \rho_k z^k. \quad (1.10)$$

If $n=0, O_\lambda^0 b(z) = b(z)$.

$0 \leq u \leq l, \partial \geq 0$

Definition 1.4. A function $f(z)$ in $\mathcal{F}$ is said to be in $O_\lambda^\eta(\xi, \rho, \omega, \partial, \lambda, l, u)$ if and only if

$$\left| \frac{\frac{z(O_\lambda^\eta(b))' - 1}{(O_\lambda^\eta(f))' - 1}}{2\xi \left(\frac{z(O_\lambda^\eta(b))' - \rho}{(O_\lambda^\eta(b))' - 1} \right) - \left(\frac{z(O_\lambda^\eta(f))' - 1}{(O_\lambda^\eta(b))' - 1} \right)} \right| < \omega \quad (1.11)$$

Where $0 \leq \rho < \frac{1}{2\xi}, 0 < \omega \leq 1, \frac{1}{2} \leq \xi \leq 1, n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$.

[9] has studied the coefficient estimates, growth theorem, distortion theorem and closure theorem for this class. He also proved the theorem which we stated here as a lemma

Lemma 1.5. $b(z) \in O_\lambda^\eta(\xi, \rho, \omega, \partial, \lambda, l, u)$ if and only if

$$\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} ([1 + (k+l-u-1)\partial]^n (1-\lambda) + \lambda^{n+k-1} C) (2\xi\omega(k-\rho) + (k-1)(1-\omega)) \varrho_k < 2\xi\omega(1-\rho) \quad (1.12)$$

$$n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}, 0 < \omega \leq 1, 0 \leq \rho < \frac{1}{2\xi}, \frac{1}{2} \leq \xi \leq 1.$$

2. Result and Discussion.

In concern with earlier works of [3],[10] and [9] we investigate the results related to $\operatorname{Re}\left\{\frac{b(z)}{b_n(z)}\right\}$, $\operatorname{Re}\left\{\frac{b_n(z)}{b'(z)}\right\}$, $\operatorname{Re}\left\{\frac{b'(z)}{b_n(z)}\right\}$, $\operatorname{Re}\left\{\frac{b_n(z)}{b'(z)}\right\}$ for the functions and their partial sum in the class $O_\lambda^\eta(\xi, \rho, \omega, \partial, \lambda, l, u)$. We also determine sharp lower bound for these real parts.

Theorem 2.1. If $b(z) \in O_\lambda^\eta(\xi, \rho, \omega, \partial, \lambda, l, u)$ then,

$$\operatorname{Re}\left\{\frac{b(z)}{b_n(z)}\right\} \geq \frac{H_{n+1} - 2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{H_{n+1}} \quad (2.1)$$

Where,

$$H_k = ([1 + (k+l-u-1)\partial]^k (1-\lambda) + \lambda^{k+l-1} C) (2\xi\omega(k-\rho) + (k-1)(1-\omega))$$

Result obtained is sharp for the following:

$$b(z) = z - \frac{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{H_{n+1}} z^n.$$

Proof: Given that $b(z) \in O_\lambda^\eta(\xi, \rho, \omega, \partial, \lambda, l, u)$

$$\therefore \sum_{k=2}^n H_k \varrho_k \leq 2\xi\omega(1-\rho)$$

Now to prove (2.1) we will show that,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega} \left[\frac{b(z)}{b_n(z)} - \frac{\frac{H_{n+1}-1}{2\xi\omega}}{\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}} \right] &= \frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega} \left[\frac{\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)b(z) - b_n(z)\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) + b_n(z)}{b_n(z)\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)} \right] \\ &= \frac{\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)b(z) - b_n(z)\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) + b_n(z)}{b_n(z)} \\ &= \frac{1+w(z)}{1-w(z)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\left[\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)b(z) - b_n(z)\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) + b_n(z) \right] [1-w(z)] = b_n(z)[1+w(z)]$$

$$\left[\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)b(z) - b_n(z)\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) + b_n(z) \right] - w(z) \left[\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)b(z) - b_n(z)\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) + b_n(z) \right] = b_n(z) + b_n(z)w(z)$$

$$\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)b(z) - b_n(z)\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) = w(z) \left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)b(z) - b_n(z)\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)w(z) + 2b_n(z)w(z)$$

$$W(z) = \frac{\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)(b(z) - b_n(z))}{2b_n(z) + \left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right)(b(z) - b_n(z))}$$

$$\begin{aligned} b(z) - b_n(z) &= (z - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k z^k) - (z - \sum_{k=2}^n a_k z^k) \\ &= -\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} a_k z^k \\ &= \left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (-\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} a_k z^k) \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore w(z) = \frac{\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (-\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} a_k z^k)}{2(z - \sum_{k=2}^n a_k z^k) - \left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} a_k z^k)}$$

$$|w(z)| = \frac{\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} a_k z^k)}{|2(z - \sum_{k=2}^n a_k z^k) - \left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} a_k z^k)|}$$

$|w(z)| < 1$ if

$$\frac{\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \varrho_k)}{2(z - \sum_{k=2}^n \varrho_k) - \left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \varrho_k)} < 1$$

$$\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \varrho_k) < 2 - 2\sum_{k=2}^n \varrho_k - \left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \varrho_k$$

$$2\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \varrho_k) \leq 2 - 2\sum_{k=2}^n \varrho_k$$

$$\left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \varrho_k) \leq 1 - \sum_{k=2}^n \varrho_k$$

$$\therefore \left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \varrho_k) + \sum_{k=2}^n \varrho_k \leq 1 \quad (2.2)$$

To show (2.2) we use (1.11). It is sufficient to show that,

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \varrho_k) + \sum_{k=2}^n \varrho_k &\leq \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left(\frac{H_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) \varrho_k \\ \left(\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega}\right) (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \varrho_k) + \sum_{k=2}^n \varrho_k &\leq \sum_{k=2}^n \left(\frac{H_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) \varrho_k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{H_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) \varrho_k \end{aligned}$$

$$1. \sum_{k=2}^n (H_k - 2\xi\omega(1-\rho))q_k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} (H_k - H_{n+1})q_k \geq 0$$

Now to prove that function is extremal, we put $z = re^{\frac{2\pi i}{n}}$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore b(z) &= z - \frac{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{H_{n+1}} z^{n+1}, \quad f_n(z) = z \\ \therefore \frac{b(z)}{b_n(z)} &= 1 - \frac{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{H_{n+1}} z^n \\ &= 1 - \frac{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{H_{n+1}} r^n \\ &= 1 - \frac{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{H_{n+1}} \quad \text{where } r \rightarrow 1^- \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.2 If $b(z) \in O_{\lambda}^{\eta}(\xi, \rho, \omega, \theta, \lambda, l, u)$, then $\operatorname{Re}\left\{\frac{b_n(z)}{b(z)}\right\} \geq \frac{H_{n+1}-4\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}$

Also for the function given below we obtain the sharp result.

$$f(z) = z - \frac{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{H_{n+1}} z^{n+1}.$$

Proof: Suppose that $b(z) \in O_{\lambda}^{\eta}(\xi, \rho, \omega, \theta, \lambda, l, u)$.

$$\therefore \sum_{k=2}^n H_k a_k \leq 2\xi\omega(1-\rho)$$

To prove this theorem, we use subordination technique used in previous theorem.

We set,

$$\frac{H_{n+1}-4\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} \left[\frac{f_n(z)}{f(z)} - \frac{H_{n+1}-4\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} \right] = \frac{1+w(z)}{1-w(z)}$$

After simple calculation we get,

$$\begin{aligned} w(z) &= \frac{\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} [b_n(z)-b(z)]}{\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} b_n(z) - \left(\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) b(z) + 2b(z)} \\ &= \frac{\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k z^k)}{2z - 2(\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} q_k z^k) + \left(\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k z^k} \end{aligned}$$

$|w(z)| < 1$ if

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k)}{2 - 2(\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} q_k) - \left(\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k} < 1 \\ \therefore \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k) &< 2 - 2(\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} q_k) - \left(\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k \\ &\therefore \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k) < 1 - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} q_k \\ \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k) + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} q_k &< 1 \end{aligned} \quad (2.3)$$

To prove (2.3) it is sufficient to show that

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k) + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} q_k \leq \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} \left(\frac{H_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) q_k \\ &\sum_{k=2}^n q_k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k + \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k) \\ &\leq \sum_{k=2}^n \left(\frac{H_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) q_k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{H_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) q_k \\ &2\xi\omega(1-\rho) \sum_{k=2}^n q_k + 2\xi\omega(1-\rho) \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k + \left(\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}\right) \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} q_k \\ &\leq \sum_{k=2}^n (H_k) q_k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} (H_k) q_k \\ \therefore \sum_{k=2}^n (H_k - 2\xi\omega(1-\rho)) q_k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} (H_k - H_{n+1}) q_k &\geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.3. If $b(z) \in O_{\lambda}^{\eta}(\xi, \rho, \omega, \theta, \lambda, l, u)$ then

$$\operatorname{Re}\left\{\frac{b'(z)}{b_n(z)}\right\} > \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{H_{n+1}}. \quad (2.4)$$

$$\text{Where, } H_k \geq \frac{H_{n+1}}{n+1} k, \quad k = n+1, n+2, \dots$$

Result is sharp for the function,

$$b(z) = z - \frac{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)}{H_{n+1}} z^{n+1}.$$

Proof. Given that $b(z) = z - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} a_k z^k \in O_{\lambda}^{\eta}(\xi, \rho, \omega, \theta, \lambda, l, u)$

$$\begin{aligned} b'(z) &= 1 - \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k a_k z^{k-1} \quad \text{and } b_n(z) = z - \sum_{k=2}^n a_k z^k \\ b'_n(z) &= 1 - \sum_{k=2}^n k a_k z^{k-1} \end{aligned}$$

To prove result we will show that,

$$\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} \left[\frac{b'(z)}{b'_n(z)} - \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{H_{n+1}} \right] < \frac{1+z}{1-z}$$

$$\text{Set } \frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} \left[\frac{b'(z)}{b'_n(z)} - \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{H_{n+1}} \right] = \frac{1+w(z)}{1-w(z)}$$

We get,

$$\begin{aligned} w(z) &= \frac{\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [b'(z)-b'_n(z)]}{\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} (b'(z)-b'_n(z))+2b'_n(z)} \\ &= \frac{\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k z^{k-1}]}{2-2\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k\varrho_k z^{k-1} + \frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k z^{k-1})} \\ &\quad |w(z)| < 1 \text{ if} \\ &\quad \frac{\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k]}{2-2\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k\varrho_k + \frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k)} < 1 \\ &\quad \frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k] < 2-2\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k\varrho_k + \frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} (\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k) \\ &\quad \frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k] + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k\varrho_k < 1 \quad (2.5) \end{aligned}$$

(2.5) will hold if

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k] + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k\varrho_k \leq \frac{\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} H_k\varrho_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} \\ &\frac{H_{n+1}}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k] + \sum_{k=2}^n k\varrho_k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k \leq \frac{\sum_{k=2}^n H_k\varrho_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} + \frac{\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} H_k\varrho_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} \\ &\sum_{k=2}^n (H_k - 2\xi\omega(1-\rho)k)\varrho_k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \left[H_k - \frac{H_{n+1}}{n+1}k \right] \varrho_k \geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

Hence hold.

Theorem 2.4. If $f(z) \in O_{\lambda}^n(\xi, \rho, \omega, \theta, \lambda, l, u)$, then

$$\text{Re} \left\{ \frac{b'_n(z)}{b'(z)} \right\} > \frac{H_{n+1}-4\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} \quad (2.6)$$

With $H_k \geq \frac{H_{n+1}}{n+1}k$, $k = n+1, n+2, \dots$

Proof: To prove result we will show that,

$$\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} \left[\frac{b'_n(z)}{b'(z)} - \frac{H_{n+1}-4\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} \right] = \frac{1+w(z)}{1-w(z)}$$

After simplification we get,

$$\begin{aligned} w(z) &= \frac{\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [b'_n(z)-b'(z)]}{2f'(z) + \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [b'_n(z)-b'(z)]} \\ &= \frac{\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k z^{k-1}]}{2-2\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k\varrho_k z^{k-1} + \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k z^{k-1}]} \end{aligned}$$

$|w(z)| < 1$, if

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k]}{2-2\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k\varrho_k - \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k]} < 1 \\ &\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k] < 2-2\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k\varrho_k - \frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k] \\ &\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k] + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k\varrho_k < 1 \quad (2.7) \end{aligned}$$

It is sufficient to show that,

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k] + \sum_{k=2}^{\infty} k\varrho_k < \frac{\sum_{k=2}^{\infty} H_k\varrho_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} \\ &\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} [\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k] + \sum_{k=2}^n k\varrho_k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} k\varrho_k < \frac{\sum_{k=2}^n H_k\varrho_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} + \frac{\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} H_k\varrho_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} \\ &\sum_{k=2}^n k\varrho_k + \left[\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{H_{n+1}-2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)(n+1)} + 1 \right) k\varrho_k \right] \leq \frac{\sum_{k=2}^n H_k\varrho_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} + \frac{\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} H_k\varrho_k}{2\xi\omega(1-\rho)} \\ &\sum_{k=2}^n (H_k - 2\xi\omega(1-\rho)k)\varrho_k + \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \left[H_k - \frac{H_{n+1}}{n+1}k \right] \varrho_k \geq 0 \end{aligned}$$

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